

Development of a Fuel Depletion Benchmark Model for the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment and Demonstration with MCNP-ADDER

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ABSTRACT

A fuel depletion benchmark model for the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) has been developed to support the development of molten salt reactor fuel depletion tools and analyses. The model is based on data aggregated from legacy reports such as a digitized power history, a starting material composition, batch material additions and removals, and experimentally measured samples used for validation or parametric inversion. The benchmark model is demonstrated through coupled neutron transport and depletion simulations over the full MSRE operational history, including the transition from ²³⁵U-based to ²³³U-based fuel. Comparisons between simulated and experimental nuclide inventories show strong agreement for salt-seeking fission products and actinide isotopic ratios, validating the benchmark's neutronic fidelity. Discrepancies for volatile or insoluble nuclides highlight the need for MSR fuel depletion simulations to implement dynamic, element-specific removal. The benchmark provides a valuable foundation for code-to-code verification of tools that couple neutron transport, fuel depletion, and chemistry, and establishes an experimental validation for liquid-fueled reactors.

Keywords: molten salt reactor experiment, fuel depletion, benchmark, MCNP, ADDER

1. INTRODUCTION

A reactor physics benchmark for the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) was recently published focusing on the physics of the reactor's first criticality with ²³⁵U fuel [1]. In order to perform analyses concerned with the fuel cycle and chemical behavior of liquid-fueled molten salt reactors (MSR), there is also motivation to develop a fuel depletion benchmark model along with corresponding simulation tools [2]. Given the experimental nature of the reactor, such as the highly intermittent operation and the various material additions and removals, the development of such a fuel depletion benchmark required considerable effort and iterative refinement after comparison to available literature.

The present work includes the assessment and digitization of various details from legacy ORNL reports, including the power history of MSRE, characterization of the material compositions added to the fuel during operation, and comparison of depletion calculations to various experimental measurements of fission products and actinides to support validation. Based on this, new fuel depletion capabilities desired for MSR applications include the ability to add and remove elements or nuclides during specific timesteps (e.g., enrichment additions) as well as continuously throughout operation (e.g., accounting for on-line fission product removal). The resulting MSRE fuel depletion benchmark model was demonstrated with neutron transport-coupled fuel depletion simulations. The present work was initiated with the fuel management and depletion software Advanced Dimensional Depletion for Engineering of Reactors (ADDER) [3] based on features preliminarily developed to aid in flowing fuel analyses, such as batch fuel modifications and the continuous removal of elements from the fuel.

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2. METHODS

The fuel depletion software ADDER was used with the Monte Carlo neutron transport software MCNP 6.2 [4] to simulate the evolution of the nuclide inventory over the MSRE operational history. To support future code-to-code benchmarking exercises, a discussion is provided on details and considerations for the present model's methods, parameters, and nuclear data.

2.1. Neutron Transport-Coupled Fuel Depletion with MCNP-ADDER

ADDER is an open-source depletion and fuel management analysis tool written in Python, and versions 1.0.0, 1.0.1, and 1.1.0 were used throughout the development of this benchmark model. ADDER couples an external neutron transport solver, such as MCNP 6.2, with an internal depletion solver in order to progress forward through time. In this common model, the transport solver is used to produce any user requested results (such as k_{eff} and any tallies) but also to provide model-specific reaction rates for the depletion solver's burnup matrix. While ADDER provides the user with the ability to use any number of neutron groups for this burnup matrix, this analysis used one-group cross sections (1GXS) for the burnup matrix; note that neutron transport in MCNP 6.2 was still performed as continuous-energy. As will be discussed in the following section, the geometry was modeled as an infinite lattice unit cell to reduce computational cost during cross-section generation. Each Monte Carlo simulation step employed 150 batches (50 inactive) of 10,000 particles per batch, corresponding to a total of 1 million active particle histories per step. These settings produce a well converged source entropy, an average 1σ standard deviation on k_{eff} of 60 pcm, and maximum relative errors (1σ) on key reaction rates of 0.1-0.2%. Consequently, each step performing flux and cross-section regeneration required approximately 10 minutes of runtime when executed in parallel with 10 MPI processes and 8 threads per process.

The total reactor power and time duration were prescribed within each depletion step in the ADDER input. Reaction rates were updated at the start of each non-zero-power depletion block by invoking MCNP to calculate the neutron flux and reaction rates, followed by Bateman equation solutions for isotopic evolution. Depletion calculations relied on the constant extrapolation/constant midpoint (CE/CM) method for numerical integration and used the internal CRAM matrix exponential solver, order 16. To support flowing-fuel analyses, ADDER also offers a MSR section where certain modeling functionalities relevant to MSRs can be utilized [3, 5]. In the MSR section, stepwise material feeds and removals can be specified by defining the material composition, density, and mass flow rate to be applied over that timestep duration, where a negative mass flow rate performs a removal of that material. This functionality is critical for modeling the on-line feeding of enrichment/reductant materials or the batch removal of certain fuel components. In ADDER's MSR section implementation of the transition matrix method, nuclide decay and chemical removal within the flow loop are applied sequentially after the burnup matrix solution at each timestep. As a result, in-loop decay and removal do not affect the reaction rate recalculations performed during that same step. This separation may lead to differences relative to spatially resolved depletion methods which inherently couple transport, depletion, and removal within a single step [6].

2.2. Nuclear Data

In this fuel depletion benchmark model, the cross-section data is derived from ENDF/B-VII.1 [7] at a temperature of 900 K (.82c) for both the fuel and graphite materials, with graphite thermal neutron scattering libraries at 1000 K ("mt2 grph.16t") [8], and no temperature-dependent interpolation is performed when calculating cross-sections. ADDER invokes MCNP to re-calculate 1GXS only for those nuclide reactions that contribute above a specified threshold to the overall system reactivity. As part of an ongoing code-to-code benchmark of the ADDER model with OpenMC, it was necessary to produce a depletion library consistent between the two codes. A new OpenMC depletion chain file in XML format was generated from the ENDF/B-VII.1 [7] data using the `openmc.deplete.Chain.from_endf` class. This was then converted to the HDF5 format (for use by ADDER) by using a custom processing script. This approach incorporates consistent decay data, neutron reaction types such as $(n,2n)$, $(n,3n)$, $(n,4n)$, (n,γ) , (n,p) , (n,α) , (n,t) , and (n,d) , and branching ratios taken from a pre-generated file aligned with a PWR neutron energy spectrum. Because ADDER does not yet accommodate energy-dependent fission

product yields, fission yields remain set to the thermal values from ENDF/B-VII.1 [7], though this has been identified as a potential future code enhancement. For power normalization, ADDER employs a hard-coded correlation from ORIGEN2 to determine the recoverable energy per fission, Q_{rec} , for each fissionable nuclide. These nuclide-specific Q -values are then averaged for each material according to the material's fission rate, before ultimately being averaged across all materials in the system. The complete correlation-based methodology is described in the ADDER v1.1.0 user guide [3].

3. FUEL DEPLETION BENCHMARK MODEL

3.1. Lattice Geometry

The reactor geometry was represented simply as an infinite lattice using constructive solid geometry in MCNP. As can be seen in Figure 1 below, the unit cell contains a depletable region of fuel salt surrounded by a non-depletable region of graphite with reflective boundary conditions in the radial direction. To improve computational efficiency, the unit cell height is represented with the nominal MSRE core lattice height of 67 inches (170.18 cm), and thus it uses a vacuum boundary condition in the axial direction to allow neutron leakage above and below the core. The resulting fuel and graphite volumes in the unit cell geometry are approximately 122.33 and 426.64 cm³, respectively.

Figure 1. Geometry of the unit cell in MCNP featuring a fuel (red) region and a graphite (green) region

It was reported in a previously published reactor physics benchmark of the MSRE [1] that the number of equivalent fuel channels in the graphite lattice (including fractional sizes) is 1140. Because the geometry utilized in the present work represents 1/4th of a full fuel channel, a factor of 4560 must be applied to normalize (reduce) the power level of the reactor, representing the ratio of the whole core volume to the unit cell volume. The resulting unscaled volume of the MSRE core fuel salt inventory is approximately 0.558 m³.

Additionally, to facilitate code-to-code benchmarking, the total fuel salt inventory in the primary loop is assumed to be irradiated as one static fuel region as opposed to a flowing salt only irradiated in the core region. Therefore, an additional normalization factor must be applied to the reactor power level that represents the ratio of the total fuel salt inventory volume to the core volume. The volumes of the various regions of the circulating loop were estimated previously [9], amounting to an unscaled primary loop volume of approximately 1.96 m³. Because this value likely does not include the fuel salt volume associated with the pump bowl such as in the pool and spray ring, these additional volumes were estimated from available specifications [10]. As a result, the unscaled volume of the total fuel salt inventory utilized in the present work is assumed to be approximately 2.05 m³, resulting in an additional normalization factor of approximately 3.676 which should also be applied to reduce the power level modeled in the ADDER depletion model.

An additional consideration for a model with static fuel involves the application of the removal rates. In reality, chemical removal may occur in different regions of the primary loop at different rates. But in the simplified one-region static fuel salt model utilized here, the fission product removal rates are applied to the entire fuel salt region continuously with respect to time and space, and therefore only represent the spatiotemporally averaged removal rates over the entire burn-up history.

3.2. Power History

To allow for proper comparison of fuel depletion calculations to the radiochemical measurements of salt samples removed from the MSRE pump bowl [9], an accurate representation of the power history must be modeled. The power history of the entire operation of MSRE was digitized from legacy ORNL reports [9, 11, 12] with a perceived time resolution uncertainty of ± 4 hours and a power resolution uncertainty of around ± 0.5 MW_{th}. If the power level was depicted as “full power”, a level of 7.4 MW_{th} [13] was used for this benchmark model. For times when the reactor was persistently ramped up and down within short periods of time, it was decided to lump the cumulative MWh of a block of power ramps into a single duration and calculate the time-averaged power level. Given the poor resolution of the documents from which the power history was digitized, it was iteratively refined by comparing against legacy predictions of the cumulative MWh [9] or equivalent full power hours [13] reported for certain dates. The average discrepancy between the digitized and reported values of these cumulative burn-up metrics is below 1% ($n > 50$ dates). The power history reported in the benchmark model presented here contains 225 timesteps of varying power levels and shutdown periods, constituting over 540 effective full-power days (EFPD) of burn-up spanning over 1,400 days of operation.

3.3. Starting Fuel Composition, Batch Modifications, and Fission Product Removal

The starting ²³⁵U fuel composition was based on the MSRE reactor physics benchmark [1] but the starting impurity concentration of oxygen was reduced from roughly 500 ppm to 50 ppm based on reported values [13]. Chemically driven changes in the fuel salt due to corrosion were not modeled; instead, Fe, Cr, and Ni were included in the initial composition and allowed to isotopically evolve through transmutation. To simplify representation of the fuel changeover, the complex operational procedures of draining, iterative flushing, uranium fluorination, and staged additions of ²³³U-bearing salt [13] were all approximated with two discrete steps: bulk removal of ²³⁵UF₄ and subsequent addition of ²³³UF₄ with additional carrier salt. During the bulk removal, it was discovered that the fluorination removal of ²³⁵UF₄ also resulted in the unintentional removal of fission product Nb from the fuel salt as well [13], evidenced by its measurement on the uranium capture beds, and further supported by the unusual shift in measurement data of ⁹⁵Nb. To allow the model to reflect this unintended circumstance, the removal of 80% of Nb was also simulated within this bulk removal step. Historical records indicate that bulk removal of ²³⁵U occurred between August 21 and September 14, 1968 [13], followed by incremental additions of ²³³UF₄ from September 14 to November 11, 1968, via capsules of approximately 50–100 g each [13]. In ADDER, this was modeled by prescribing one-day batch operations in which the normalized mass and isotopics of the ²³⁵UF₄ was removed, followed by the addition of ²³³UF₄ and carrier salt. Because details are scarce on the exact isotopic composition and mass of uranium added, this was calculated by comparing the composition in the prior ADDER step with that desired as the target composition. The target uranium isotopic composition and mass were taken from Table 7.4 and Table 3.1 in Ref. [13], respectively, with an additional mass of carrier salt as mentioned in Ref [14]. Enrichment operations during both modes also occurred sporadically involving capsule additions of ²³⁵U [11], ²³³U, or ²³⁹Pu [13], and reductant additions for salt redox control were also accounted for [13]. The effect of on-line fission product removal can also be simulated with ADDER by implementing removal rates for multiple fission product elements (Table I). These were inferred by iteratively comparing simulation results with experimental data for two dozen fission product isotopes that were radiochemically measured. It should be noted that these rates are physically representative of the continuous elemental removal from a one-region fuel depletion model to match experimental data specific to MSRE. Depletion models with multiple interconnected regions of varying volumes and residence times (representing a discretization of the primary loop) would require removal rate values specific to the region in which they are applied. Efforts are ongoing to develop such multi-region depletion models to account for flowing fuel effects in anticipation of in-loop measurements of short-lived fission products.

Table I. Fission product removal rates (s^{-1}) applied continuously in ADDER throughout the power history

Kr, Xe	Rb, Cs	Mo, Tc, Ru, Ag, Te	Nb, Sb, Br, I
5.0E-04	8.0E-09	6.0E-06	1.0E-06

4. MCNP-ADDER SIMULATION RESULTS

The operators of MSRE extracted 60 salt samples from the pump bowl over the course of both modes of operation, and radiochemically measured up to 24 different fission products within each sample via gamma spectrometry [9]. Several measurements were performed to characterize uranium and plutonium isotopics in extracted salt samples as well. These datasets currently serve as the only source of experimental characterization data that could support the validation of fuel depletion simulations for flowing fuel reactors. ADDER calculations are presented in comparison to these datasets, serving as both a preliminary validation of the software (e.g., depletion solution methods) as well as a validation of the benchmark model details (e.g., power history details or fission product removal rates).

First, ADDER calculation results without the use of continuous fission product removal provides a baseline comparison of the salt-seeking nuclides with the experimental measurements and can offer a validation of the calculation method and power history. The distribution of calculated-to-experimental ratios (C/E) for these nuclides is presented in Figure 2. In the boxplot, the shaded region denotes the interquartile range (IQR), corresponding to the central 50% of the data. Whiskers extend to the most extreme values within ± 1.5 times the IQR, while values outside this range are represented as individual points. Despite the small sample size and low experimental precision, the IQRs for all salt-seeking nuclides remain generally centered around unity. Additionally, the mean and median C/E results for twelve fission products that exhibit higher volatility in the fuel are shown in Table II. These calculated values are generally 1 to 30x larger than the measured values, a consequence of the complex transport behavior of each fission product element and their decay precursors. In general, the high C/E values highlight the need for fission product element removal rates in the depletion model to accurately represent the chemical effects of the primary loop.

Figure 2. Distribution of values for the ratio of ADDER-calculated values (assuming no fission product removal) to experimental values (C/E) of twelve salt-seeking fission products measured on various dates [9]

Table II. Mean and median values for the ratio of ADDER-calculated values (assuming no fission product removal) to experimental values (C/E) of twelve volatile fission products measured on various dates [9]

Nuclide	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Nuclide	Mean	Median	Std Dev
Nb95	87.97	5.87	369.87	Te129m	35.33	4.75	69.71
Mo99	65.56	3.49	140.60	Te132	137.41	11.89	423.20
Ru103	325.00	28.63	653.83	I131	2.59	1.71	2.53
Ru106	404.07	32.57	882.18	I133	1.36	1.37	0.02
Ag111	24.57	10.69	54.95	I135	1.41	1.49	0.29

The fission product removal rates in Table I were refined until C/E values closer to unity were found. The resulting impact of these removal rates on the calculated inventory can be seen in Figure 3 below for ^{131}I , predominantly impacted by the removal of iodine and its decay precursor tellurium. It is noteworthy that the C/E values for iodine are generally higher during ^{233}U operation than during ^{235}U operation, which can be seen for other fission products as well. A comparison of C/E values between the two modes of operation is provided in Table III for twelve other nuclides (including those with at least four measurement samples in each mode of operation).

Figure 3. Comparing ADDER calculations (with and without fission product removal) to experimental values of ^{131}I measured on various dates during operation [9]

Table III. Comparing C/E Ratios between the ^{235}U and ^{233}U modes of operation based on calculations applying continuous fission product removal rates

Nuclide	^{235}U Operation			^{233}U Operation		
	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Mean	Median	Std Dev
Sr89	1.04	1.02	0.13	1.20	1.08	0.53
Ba140	0.98	0.96	0.28	1.25	0.94	0.84
Ce141	1.13	1.00	0.36	0.99	0.95	0.14
Ce144	0.83	0.83	0.05	0.94	0.84	0.43
Zr95	1.19	0.97	0.80	1.10	1.01	0.45
Nb95	56.31	1.32	138.99	3.54	1.22	4.17
Mo99	20.50	0.68	48.67	35.92	2.04	111.82
Ru103	16.25	0.77	34.90	8.17	1.20	15.83
Ru106	1.90	0.26	3.95	2.05	0.07	6.09
Ag111	1.61	1.69	0.16	4.84	2.37	11.50
Te129m	0.67	0.31	1.01	3.38	0.50	6.19
Te132	13.55	2.08	30.61	71.14	10.66	173.88
I131	0.68	0.59	0.43	1.53	1.14	1.20

It can be seen that the C/E values are higher in the ^{233}U mode than the ^{235}U mode for nearly all volatile fission products and generally in agreement for all salt-seekers. This may be explained by reports indicating that the void fraction was approximately an order of magnitude greater under ^{233}U operation [15]; the influence of bubble sparging on noble metal transport and the volatilization of iodine has been discussed [15]. It should be emphasized that the simulations assume the same maximum reactor power level ($7.4 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$) in both modes of operation. If the actual power level during ^{233}U operation exceeded that of ^{235}U operation, this could partially explain the observed discrepancy in C/E values. But notably, the C/E values for salt-seeking nuclides do not show significant differences between the two operating modes, supporting the conclusion that the assumed power history is sufficiently accurate. As a result, it is evident that removal rate values for most of these fission product elements likely need to be dynamic and higher during the ^{233}U mode of operation.

Analytical measurements of uranium and plutonium isotopes were also performed via mass spectrometry of fuel salt samples for a limited number of dates during operation. Details regarding the sample measurement method are sparse and the analytical results are often reported as an isotopic composition and not always as absolute quantities in the primary loop. Consequently, the experimental data is used in the form of isotopic ratios to validate the neutronic accuracy of the simplified lattice geometry of the depletion model, as can be seen in Figure 4 below. For example, during ^{235}U and ^{233}U operation, the generation of ^{236}U and ^{234}U , respectively, is proportional to burn-up and can be used as validation for cross-section calculation. Similarly, due to production of ^{239}Pu during the ^{235}U mode of operation and the intentional addition of PuF_3 during the ^{233}U mode of operation, plutonium isotopic ratios can be used to validate not only the neutronic accuracy of the model but also the software's material addition and removal functionalities. Because details were sometimes sparse on the actinide isotopic compositions of the materials added to and removed from the reactor, certain benchmark model details were iteratively refined through trial-and-error comparison with experimental data.

Figure 4. Calculated uranium isotopic ratios indicative of burn-up compared to analytical measurements [13]

5. CONCLUSIONS

A fuel depletion benchmark model for the MSRE was developed and demonstrated using MCNP-ADDER to reproduce experimental isotopic data across both ^{235}U and ^{233}U operations. The benchmark integrates a detailed power history, batch material modifications, and continuous fission product removal, enabling realistic simulation of MSR fuel evolution. Comparison with experimental data validates the neutronic accuracy of the model and highlights the importance of implementing removal rates for insoluble species. The benchmark establishes a robust foundation towards the validation of modeling and simulation tools of liquid-fueled reactor systems but concerns with MSRE data quality and sparsity highlight the need for the development of benchmarks based on future planned MSRs.

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